

The Purépecha

Secondary source

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Mesoamerican Religions, Tarascan, Language, Tarascan, Purepecha

The Purépecha (also known as P'urhépecha or Tarascan) inhabited the highlands and lake regions of the Mexican state of Michoacán. One of the most prominent civilizations in Mesoamerica, they built a powerful city-state known as the Tarascan state. They were among the few civilizations to successfully resist the Aztec Empire and spoke a distinctive language unrelated to those of neighboring communities. The Purépecha are also known for being one of the few civilizations in Mesoamerica with advanced metalworking. They crafted tools, ornaments and weapons using copper and silver, among other metals. Their territory, centered around Lake Pátzcuaro, was organized into a strong centralized political system with a capital at Tzintzuntzan. The state was ruled by a hereditary leader called the Cazonci, supported by a network of regional administrators. The Purépecha maintained a military structure and a bureaucratic government that allowed them to expand and defend their territory effectively. Religion played a central role in Purépecha life. Their pantheon included deities associated with fire, sun, and war, such as Curicaueri, their main deity. Human sacrifices were common offerings to deities, practiced by religious specialists. Unlike many Mesoamerican cultures, the Purépecha language has no known relation to any other language family in the region. Despite colonization and forced conversion, Purépecha identity remains strong to this date, and has become a symbol for the modern state of Michoacán. Many of their practices, customs, political and social structures were vastly recorded in the 16th century document written by Fray Jerónimo de Alcalá. This document is known as *Relación de Michoacán* and has long inspired nation-wide interest in studying the Purépecha Empire.

Date Range: 1300 CE - 1530 CE

Region: Western Mexico

Region tags: Mesoamerica (general), Mesoamerica, Mexico

The Purépecha Empire inhabited the region of Western Mexico, around lake Patzcuaro and the state now known as Michoacán.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Fuente 1: Corona Núñez, J. *Mitología Tarasca*. Morelia: Instituto Michoacano de Cultura, 1999.
- Fuente 2: Pollard, H.P. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.
- Fuente 3: Williams, E. "The Tarascan Empire in the Mesoamerican Ecumene." In *Ancient West Mexico: Archaeology and Culture History*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2019.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- URL de la Fuente 1: <http://etzakutarakua.colmich.edu.mx/proyectos/relaciondemichoacan/default.asp>
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: El Colegio de Michoacán. "Proyecto Relación de Michoacán," 2008. <http://etzakutarakua.colmich.edu.mx/proyectos/relaciondemichoacan/default.asp>.

- URL de la Fuente 2: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/137/13710406.pdf
 - Descripción de la Fuente 2: Monzón, C. “Los Principales Dioses Tarascos: Un Ensayo de Análisis Etimológico En La Cosmología Tarasca.” *Relaciones* 26, no. 104 (2005): 136–68.
 - URL de la Fuente 3: <https://archive.org/details/tarascanciviliza0000gore>
 - Descripción de la Fuente 3: Gorenstein, S., and H.P. Pollard. *The Tarascan Civilization: A Late Prehispanic Cultural System*. Nashville: Vanderbilt University, 1983.
- Notes: The digital project by El Colegio de Michoacán (source 1) offers a curated bibliographic database and academic resources dedicated to the *Relación de Michoacán*. It acts as a complement to the original chronicle.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- URL de la Fuente 1: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.calmecacanahuac.com/amoxtin/RELACIONDEMICHOACAN
 - Descripción de la Fuente 1: Alcalá Jerónimo de, 2008, *Relación de Michoacán*, El Colegio de Michoacán, México.
- Notes: The *Relación de Michoacán* is a 16th-century colonial chronicle commissioned by Viceroy Antonio de Mendoza and authored by Franciscan friar Jerónimo de Alcalá. It documents the history, religious beliefs, political organization, and cultural practices of the Purépecha (or Tarascan) people of western Mexico prior to Spanish conquest. Based on indigenous oral accounts and pictorial manuscripts, the *Relación* is likely to be the foundational primary source in Tarascan ethnohistory.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Sí

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Sí

Notes: The Purépecha Empire maintained persistent violent conflict with the neighboring Mexica (Aztecs) Empire. These two powers never formed a political alliance, and several documented military campaigns occurred along their shared frontier. (Williams, 2019) The Aztecs attempted to expand into the Tarascan-controlled area of the Toluca Valley but were decisively repelled in the 1470s. (Hassig, 1988)

Reference: Williams, E.. “The Tarascan Empire in the Mesoamerican Ecumene”. In *Ancient West Mexico: Archaeology and Culture History*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2019.

Reference: Hassig, R.. *Aztec Warfare: Imperial Expansion and Political Control*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1988.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Religious affiliation was primarily assigned at birth, particularly within elite clans such as the Uacúsecha (ruling dynasty). Children born into these lineages inherited religious status and responsibilities, especially ceremonial roles. There is no evidence of conversion or affiliation outside this structure. (Pollard, 1993; 2008). As most Mesoamerican religions, however, it was also deeply integrated

into the social and cultural structure of the community.

Reference: Pollard, H.P. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. "A Model of the Emergence of the Tarascan State". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 217-30.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence of outreach beyond imperial conquest. The religion spread via military-political incorporation of conquered communities, not through proselitism. (Williams, 2019)

Reference: Williams, E.. "The Tarascan Empire in the Mesoamerican Ecumene". In *Ancient West Mexico: Archaeology and Culture History*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2019.

Does the religion have official political support

– Sí

Notes: The Purepecha empire was theocratic. The Irecha/Cazonci held supreme religious authority, claiming descent from deities such as Curicaueri and controlling state-sponsored rituals. Religious and political were fused roles. (Pollard 1993, Williams 2019)

Reference: Williams, E.. "The Tarascan Empire in the Mesoamerican Ecumene". In *Ancient West Mexico: Archaeology and Culture History*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2019.

Reference: Pollard, H.P. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no documented concept of apostasy (i.e., formal abandonment of religious belief) in the pre-Columbian Tarascan system. Religious practices were deeply imbedded in communal identity, meaning shifting away meant social rupture beyond religious betrayal. (Alcala, 2008) No source consulted records sanctions against apostasy.

Reference: de Alcalá , Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no comprehensive empire-wide comprehensive study that is able to give a proper estimate. Pollard (2008) estimated an approximate of 48, 000 people living around the Pátzcuaro Basin alone during the late Postclassical period. Pollard and Gorenstein (1980) concluded that the Pátzcuaro Lake Basin, the core geopolitical zone, likely exceeded the local ecological carrying capacity, implying that food imports were necessary, thus suggesting a large population size.

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. "A Model of the Emergence of the Tarascan State". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 217-30.

Reference: Pollard, H.P., and S. Gorenstein. "Agrarian Potential, Population, and the Tarascan State". *Science* 209, no. 4453 (1980): 274-77.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It is reasonable to assume that the majority of the population in Purépecha (Tarascan) empire were active member of the religious group, making it likely that the number of adherents aligned with the overall population.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

— No

Notes: Religious transmission and tradition among the Purépecha were entirely oral, passed down through generations. This was one of the primary challenges in reconstructing their cultural and religious systems (Alcalá, 2008).

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

— Sí

Notes: The architectural diversity associated with Purépecha religion includes platforms, plazas, and elite residences (Fisher et al., 2019; Acosta, 1939). Among these, the Yácata pyramids are particularly notable for their distinctive keyhole-shaped design, formed by the combination of circular and rectilinear elements joined by a central platform.

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius. "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510–28.

Reference: Acosta, J.R.. "Exploraciones Arqueológicas Realizadas En El Estado De Michoacán Durante Los Años 1937 Y 1938". *Revista Mexicana De Estudios Antropológicos* 3, no. 2 (1939): 85–98.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Archaeological evidence from Angamuco shows over 40,000 architectural foundations within its estimated boundaries: commoner and elite dwellings, ritual platforms, pyramids, storage facilities, ball courts, and a hierarchical road network (Fisher et al., 2019).

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius. "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510–28.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

— Square meters: 442

Notes: According to Fisher et al. (2019), the largest Yácata has a circular section with "dimensions of 17.5 × 19 m, whereas the rectilinear section is 34 × 13 m" (516).

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius . "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510–28.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Altura, en metros:: 6

Notes: According to Fisher et al. (2019), when referring to religious buildings, "the overall height of the structure is approximately 6 m tall" (516).

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius . "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510–28.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 0.82

Notes: Monuments varied significantly in size. Average sized was dependent on the type of structure. Altar average size, for example, was around .82m (Fisher et al. 2019). Several archeological studies have documented them, they are typically rectangular in form and feature a series of small steps (Acosta, 1939).

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius . "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510–28.

Reference: Acosta, J.R.. "Exploraciones Arqueológicas Realizadas En El Estado De Michoacán Durante Los Años 1937 Y 1938". *Revista Mexicana De Estudios Antropológicos* 3, no. 2 (1939): 85–98.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Only members of elite families have been found interred, often accompanied by offerings (Pollard et al., 1999).

Reference: Pollard, H.P., and L. Cahue. "Mortuary Patterns of Regional Elites in the Lake Patzcuaro Basin of Western Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 10, no. 3 (1999): 259–80.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of communal or centralized cemeteries.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Yácata pyramids (temples) functioned as sacred spaces tied to the state-religion, it was usually associated with the adoration of the deity Curicaueri (Pollard, 2008)

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. "A Model of the Emergence of the Tarascan State". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 217-30.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Altars were a commonly documented type of ritual monument; founded in the middle of plazas or patios (Fisher et al., 2019).

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius . "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510-28.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Settlements served different functions: open plazas connected buildings, landforms, and roads, while sunken plazas likely belonged to extended households. Smaller courtyards, or patios, were probably used by elite groups (Fisher et al., 2019).

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius . "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510-28.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– En el hogar

– En algunos espacios públicos

Notes: Besides the ceremonial architectural stonework (Fisher et al., 2019), the remains of ceramic pottery have been found in both elite and commoner contexts, but not in association with political or religious functions. Rather, they seem to reflect trade and everyday economic activity across all social strata (Hirshman, 2008).

Reference: Hirshman, A.J.. "Tarascan Ceramic Production and Implications for Ceramic

Distribution". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 299-310.

Reference: Fisher, C.T., A.S. Cohen, and R. Solinis-Casparius. "A Typology of Ancient Purépecha (tarascan) Architecture from Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 3 (2019): 510-28.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: With the expansion of the empire, analyses of ceramic products revealed innovations in pottery, including changes in form, decorative styles, and geochemical composition (Cohen, 2024; Begun, 2008).

Reference: Cohen, A.S. "Potting Communities and Conservatism in the Purépecha Empire at Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 35, no. 2 (2024): 588-97.

Reference: Begun, E.. "The Many Faces of Figurines: Figurines as Markers of Ethnicity in Michoacan". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 311-18.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Sí

Notes: The style varied depending on the region within the empire. For example, while the Chupicuaro style figurines eye style were more diamond or squinted shape, within the Patzcuaro style eyes were shaped like coffee beans (Begun, 2008).

Reference: Begun, E.. "The Many Faces of Figurines: Figurines as Markers of Ethnicity in Michoacan". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 311-18.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Sí

Notes: Researchers have also described imperial-style ceramics characterized by spouts, globular supports, polychrome decorations, intricate drawings and wax-resist firing (Cohen, 2024; Cabrera Castro, 1996).

Reference: Cabrera Castro, R.. "Cerámica Suntuaria De Tzintzuntzan, Michoacán". In *Tiempo Y Territorio En Arqueología: El Centro Norte De México*. Mexico City: Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, 1996.

Reference: Cohen, A.S.. "Potting Communities and Conservatism in the Purépecha Empire at Angamuco, Michoacán, Mexico". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 35, no. 2 (2024): 588-97.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Sí

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Sí

Notes: According to Purépecha beliefs, there are three animic components that separate from the body at death, each with distinct roles. Mintzita is the vital force located in the heart, head, and blood; it sustains life and travels to the afterlife realm after death, remaining linked to mental activity. Zuanda, often translated as "shadow," is more accurately related to breath or air; it is a cold element tied to the head that disperses or lingers near the place of death, sometimes appearing as a ghost or animal, especially if rituals were not properly followed. Jurhiata is a warm component associated with the sun and the soft spot of the skull (mollera). (González, 2013)

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Sí

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Sí (especifique): The distinguished three different animic components: Mintzita, Zuanda and Jurhiata

Belief in afterlife:

– Sí

Notes: The Purépecha believed in a dual afterlife, where the fate of the soul depended on the merits and role of the individual during life. Most people were thought to go to the Ynfierno, an underworld associated with the earth, which was not a place of punishment but rather a continuation of earthly life. There, the dead lived in villages, worked, drank, and engaged in familiar activities, often in skeletal form. Access to this realm was imagined through caves, cracks in the earth, or watery passages. In contrast, the cielo (sky or heaven) was a stratified and sacred space reserved for the gods and for those who had distinguished themselves through sacrifice, warfare, or religious leadership. It was home to deities such as Curicaueri and the “mother of the gods” and represented a divine reward for those who had earned it. Only those who had served the gods well were believed to ascend (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. “Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos”. *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Sí

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Sí

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Sí

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Sí

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: According to the *Relación de Michoacán* (de Alcalá, 2008), the Tarascans believed that the soul (ánima) survived death and traveled to different places, like “El cielo” (where the gods and those deemed worthy would go) or “Ynfierno” (where the others would go) (see also: González, 2013). It is also described that they believed life that the afterlife resembled life on earth, which is why the dead were buried with objects and, in the case of nobles, even with sacrificed individuals to accompany them.

Reference: de Alcalá , Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Reference: González, R.M.. “Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos”. *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Sí

↳ Cremation:

– Sí

Notes: Warrior who died in battle were often cremated. Their ashes were placed in funerary urns with offerings. (González, 2013)

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Mummification:

– Sí

Notes: *Relacion de Michoacan* (de Alcalá, 2008) has one specific mention of the embalming of a ruler's son, venerated as a deity after death. (González, 2013)

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

↳ Interment:

– Sí

Notes: Direct inhumation was widespread, including burials in pits, tombs, temples, platforms, and civic-ceremonial buildings. Bodies were often placed in a "flexed" position. (González, 2013)

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Sí

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Sí

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Sí

Notes: Relación de Michoacán (de Alcalá, 2008) narrates cases of people condemned to death that were left to be devoured by vultures and carrion birds as an offering to the god of the underworld (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Secondary burial:

– Sí

Notes: There is evidence of ossuaries and reburial or reuse of bones, including the placement of old bones alongside new burials (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Re-treatment of corpse:

– Sí

Notes: Human remains were sometimes handled again—e.g., bones of the deceased were reused in rituals or as amulets, especially in the case of sorcery or ancestor veneration (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Sí (especifique): musicians, precious offerings, symbolic orientation, human sacrifices and architectural elements.

Notes: Especially in the case of rulers: cremation rituals involved musicians, precious offerings, symbolic orientation toward the east, human sacrifices, and architectural elements like special tombs (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Sí

Human sacrifices present:

– Sí

Notes: Co-sacrifices were a significant element Purépecha burial practices, though mostly for the elite class. The *Relación de Michoacán* (de Alcalá, 2008) and supporting archaeological evidence indicate that when a ruler or other high-status individual died, human companions—such as servants, wives, or captives—were ritually sacrificed and buried or cremated alongside them. The bodies of sacrificial victims were often deposited in urns, grouped together in ossuaries, or buried behind temples and civic structures (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos".

Anales De Antropología 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:
– Sí

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:
– Sí

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:
– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:
– No

Are grave goods present:

– Sí

↳ Personal effects:
– Sí

Notes: The deceased were buried or cremated with items they used in life, such as bows, arrows, clothing, jewelry, and ritual instruments (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Valuable items:
– Sí

Notes: Elite burials often included precious objects like gold and silver shields (rodela), plumage headdresses, ceramic vessels, and beads (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):
– Sí

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):
– Sí

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Sí

Notes: Funerary contexts also included offerings of food and drink, urns, musical instruments, and sacrificed individuals (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

Are formal burials present:

– Sí

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Sí

Notes: Yácata 3 in Tzintzuntzan, the Central Plaza of Tres Cerritos, and Plaza Hundida are some examples of areas designated as cemeteries in Purépecha culture (González, 2013)

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Sí

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Sí

Notes: Domestic burials were common. Bodies have been found beneath residential platforms, household spaces, and within domestic structures.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Sí

Notes: Curicaueri was the supreme deity and god of the sun, fire and warfare. Cuerauáperi was a female god associated with the earth and fertility. These two gods were considered the most important within the Purépecha cosmology. Other gods included: Xaratanga, goddess of moon and water; Tzitzíqui god of rain and water; the god of the Ynfierno; and the Tirípeme gods, a group of four deities said to have helped structure the world. (Monzón, 2005; Corona Núñez, 1999).

Reference: Monzón, C.. "Los Principales Dioses Tarascos: Un Ensayo De Análisis Etimológico En La Cosmología Tarasca". *Relaciones* 26, no. 104 (2005): 136-68.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Sí

Notes: Curicaueri was the supreme deity of the Purépecha (Tarascan) empire. He was revered primarily as the god of fire, the sun, and warfare. His worship was closely tied to the legitimacy of rulers, especially the irecha (king) (Monzón, 2005).

Reference: Monzón, C.. "Los Principales Dioses Tarascos: Un Ensayo De Análisis Etimológico En La Cosmología Tarasca". Relaciones 26, no. 104 (2005): 136–68.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Sí

Notes: Curicaueri was seen as the Divine Patron of the Uacúsecha Dynasty (the ruling dynasty) (González Torres, 2005).

Reference: González Torres, Y.. Diccionario De Mitología Y Religión De Mesoamérica. Madrid: Larousse, 2005.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Sí

Notes: The ruling dynasty (uacúsecha) claimed divine descent or patronage from Curicaueri (de Alcalá, 2008; Hurtado Mendoza, 1986)

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. Relación De Michoacán. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Reference: Hurtado Mendoza, F.. La Religión De Los Purépechas: Un Testimonio Del Pueblo Tarasco. Morelia: Linotipografía Omega, 1986.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Sí

Notes: Curicaueri is believed to be aware of human affairs and sometimes interceded on behalf of them (warfare, kingship, etc.) (Monzón, 2005).

Reference: Monzón, C.. "Los Principales Dioses Tarascos: Un Ensayo De Análisis Etimológico En La Cosmología Tarasca". Relaciones 26, no. 104 (2005): 136-68.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do

(future sight):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Sí

Notes: Curicaueri is believed to influence battles, legitimized rulers, and was often invoked for protection, success, and divine guidance (Monzón, 2005; Ramírez, 1956). He could also punish by causing losses in battles and illness.

Reference: Monzón, C. "Los Principales Dioses Tarascos: Un Ensayo De Análisis Etimológico En La Cosmología Tarasca". *Relaciones* 26, no. 104 (2005): 136–68.

Reference: Ramírez, F.C.. Ireti Khatape. *Ensayo De Una Interpretación De La Relación De Michoacán. Personajes Y Dioses Michoacanos*. México: Casa Ramírez Editores, 1956.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Sí

Notes: Early colonial accounts did not clear show whether Curicaueri displayed positive emotions when receiving offerings. Offerings and sacrifices were mostly done to "please" the god. However, it's stated in several sources, including *Relación de Michoacán*, that he would become angry or displeased if rituals were neglected or improperly performed (de Alcalá, 2008; Hurtado Mendoza, 1986; Corona Núñez, 1946)

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Reference: Hurtado Mendoza, F.. *La Religión De Los Purépechas: Un Testimonio Del Pueblo Tarasco*. Morelia: Linotipografía Omega, 1986.

Reference: Corona Núñez, J.. "La Religión De Los Tarascos". *Anales Del Museo Michoacano* 4, no. 2 (1946): 13–38.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Sí

Notes: As a sun and fire deity, Curicaueri was "fed" through offerings and ritual sacrifices (González Torres, 2005).

Reference: González Torres, Y.. Diccionario De Mitología Y Religión De Mesoamérica. Madrid: Larousse, 2005.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Sí

Notes: According to the Relación de Michoacán, Curicaueri often revealed his will or commands to the cazonci (ruler) or priests through dreams or signs during rituals (de Alcalá, 2008)

Reference: de Alcalá , Jerónimo. Relación De Michoacán. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Sí

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Sí

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Sí

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Sí

Notes: Spirits were not directly seen or felt. Zuanda, one of the three animic components of the soul, is perceived as a cold element tied to the head that disperses or lingers near the place of death, sometimes appearing as a ghost or animal. Relación de Michoacán is unclear in terms of how the Purépecha interacted with the spirits, but more recent ethnographical and ethno-historic studies recount stories of spirits of former rulers parading and dancing through the streets (García Mora, 2013).

Reference: García Mora, C.. Diccionario De Lengua Phorhepecha. México: Tsimarhu/ Estudio de Etnólogos, 2013.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It could be argued that humans kept some knowledge of the world after their death. The three animic components of the soul (Mintzita, Zuanda and Jurhiata) could manifest themselves under different circumstances. Zuanda, for example, could appear as a ghost or animal if rituals were not performed properly. Mintzita, the vital force that travels to the afterlife, is said to remain linked to mental activity. (González, 2013) Accounts on how much actual knowledge spirits or souls retained after death are unclear.

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". Anales De Antropología 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Zuanda (one of the three animic components of the soul), could appear as a ghost or animal if rituals were not performed properly. It was, however, interpreted more as a consequence of an act on earth (González, 2013).

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". Anales De Antropología 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Sí

Notes: Mintzita (one of the three animic components of the soul) is said to remain linked to mental activity after death (González, 2013). It was the vital force that travel to the afterlife, where life would develop in a similar way as it was during the human's life.

Reference: González, R.M.. "Muerte Y Destinos Post Mortem Entre Los Tarascos Prehispánicos". *Anales De Antropología* 47, no. 1 (2013): 211-42.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Sí

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Sí

Notes: Spirits of ancestors were understood to remain present and active within community life, often through ritual and memory (García Mora, 2013).

Reference: García Mora, C.. *Diccionario De Lengua Phorhepecha*. México: Tsimarhu/ Estudio de Etnólogos, 2013.

↳ In dreams:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: More recent studies have compiled stories of certain human spirits and deities appearing in sacred sites, like Pátzcuaro or Zacapu (García Mora, 2013). It is unclear whether these beliefs date back to pre-colonial era or if they are a result of the religious syncretism that came after the Spanish conquest.

Reference: García Mora, C.. *Diccionario De Lengua Phorhepecha*. México: Tsimarhu/ Estudio de Etnólogos, 2013.

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Sí
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Sí
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Sí
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Sí
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Sí
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Sí

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Sí

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Sí

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Sí

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Sí

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Sí

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Sí

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Sí

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Some recent archaeological and ethnographic sources on current Purépecha communities (García Mora, 2013; Corona Núñez, 1946; Peña Delgado, 1980) suggest specific areas where supernatural oversight was believed to occur, although these actions could also be a result of religious syncretism processes after Spanish arrival. Some other authors, like Márquez Joaquín (1994), have also developed comprehensive lists of beliefs and sayings that could potentially be traced back to pre-colonial era. These sayings include stories spread through oral tradition. Spirits are active protagonists in these stories, and often influence actions and daily life.

Reference: Márquez Joaquín, P.. "Dichos Y Creencias P'urhépecha". *Relaciones* 15, no. 59 (1994): 273-95.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– El campo lo desconoce

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Like all Mesoamerican cultures, religious morality and norms were deeply imbedded into the social fabric. The political figure of the Cazonci (or king), often employed religious ideology to reinforce control and legitimacy (Pollard, 1993).

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Relación de Michoacán describes married priests (petámütis) performing rituals and playing ceremonial roles alongside nobles. It also narrates accounts of complex marriage and family structures, including polygamy among nobles and sexual roles integrated into ritual life (de Alcalá, 2008).

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. Relación De Michoacán. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to Curicaueri included tobacco balls, fine woven blankets (quapimecua), and even blood from self-sacrifice (Martínez González, 2022).

Reference: Martínez González, R.. "Los Tarascos Ante El Sacrificio Humano". Itinerarios: Revista De Estudios Lingüísticos, Literarios, Históricos Y Antropológicos, no. 36 (2022): 143–63.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There are multiple references to human sacrifice and ritual violence among the Purépecha; some individuals were offered as tribute to deities, often in the context of warfare, favor-searching or justice (Campos-Hernández et al., 2024; Martínez González, 2022). However, there is no evidence that such practices were a condition of membership in the religious group.

Reference: Martínez González, R.. "Los Tarascos Ante El Sacrificio Humano". *Itinerarios: Revista De Estudios Lingüísticos, Literarios, Históricos Y Antropológicos*, no. 36 (2022): 143-63.

Reference: Campos-Hernández, C.M.. "Ritual Human Sacrifice Among the Tarascans of West Mexico". In *Ritual Human Sacrifice in Mesoamerica*. United States: Springer International Publishing, 2024.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Sí

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: Tobacco balls, fine woven blankets (quapimecua) are some examples of the items that were given to Curicaueri as offerings. The ritual involved having these items thrown into the fire as offerings to the god (Martínez González, 2022).

Reference: Martínez González, R.. "Los Tarascos Ante El Sacrificio Humano". *Itinerarios: Revista De Estudios Lingüísticos, Literarios, Históricos Y Antropológicos*, no. 36 (2022): 143-63.

↳ Other:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Sí

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Sí

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Sí

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Sí

Notes: The *Relación de Michoacán* (de Alcalá, 2008) describes how families maintained domestic altars with fire, incense, and offerings to household gods or ancestors.

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Sí

Notes: Participation in large, state-sponsored rituals was fundamental. Descriptions of large ceremonies at *yácatas* (temples) directed towards deities like Curicaueri, are said to involve mass offerings, dances, sacred fire maintenance, and public sacrifice. These events were led by priests (*petámutis*) and nobles. Commoners were usually required to attend or contribute offerings (Pollard, 1993; de Alcalá, 2008).

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Reference: Pollard, H.P. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Sí

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Sí

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Un imperio

Notes: This classification is supported by the centralized political structure, territorial expansion, and integration of diverse ethnic groups under the authority of the Cazonci. The *Relación de Michoacán* (de Alcalá, 1980), the principal colonial account of Tarascan society, describes a complex administrative and religious system that governed over 75,000 km² prior to the Spanish arrival.

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

— Yes

Notes: Access to food was deeply stratified. For example, meat consumption was largely reserved for the nobility and was only made available to the broader population during ceremonial occasions. (González Rivadeneira et al., 2022)

Reference: González Rivadeneira, T., A. Casas, and A. Argueta Villamar. "Food Sovereignty of the P'urhépecha of Michoacán, Mexico: Historical Review and Critical Perspectives from Nature-culture Relationships". *Journal of Ethnic Foods* 9, no. 1 (2022): 1-15.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The Tarascan administration, overseen by local chiefs or caciques appointed by the *cazonci*, collected staple goods through a hierarchical tribute system and managed their storage and redistribution via official state storehouses (LaCerva, 2017; Pollard 2016).

Reference: LaCerva, D.. *Purépecha Y Pescado: Food, Status, and Conquest in 16th Century Michoacán*. Master of Arts Thesis. OhioLINK Electronic Theses and Dissertations Center: University of Toledo, 2017.

Reference: Pollard, H.P., S. Kurnick, and J. Baron. "Ruling "purépecha Chichimeca" in a Tarascan World". In *Political Strategies in Pre-columbian Mesoamerica*. United States: University Press of Colorado, 2016.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

— No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Notes: The redistribution of goods was managed by the state administration. Officials known as *quengue* oversaw state storehouses where tribute was centralized (Paredes, 1996; Gorenstein and Pollard; 1983)

Reference: Paredes, C.. "La Estratificación Social De Los Tarascos". *Arqueología Mexicana* 4, no. 19 (1996): 34-39.

Reference: Gorenstein, S., and H.P. Pollard. *The Tarascan Civilization: A Late Prehispanic Cultural System*. Nashville: Vanderbilt University, 1983.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

— Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

— No

Notes: de Alcalá's description (2008) recounts that knowledge was non-institutional, hereditary, and transmitted through ceremonial practice.

Reference: de Alcalá, Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

— No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

— Yes

Notes: They maintained a strict social hierarchy, with the nobility also divided into the royal dynasty, upper nobility, and lower nobility (Pollard, 2008).

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. "A Model of the Emergence of the Tarascan State". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 19, no. 2 (2008): 217-30.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

— Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

— Yes

Notes: The Cazonci appointed local chiefs that would in turn administer public food storage (LaCerva, 2017)

Reference: LaCerva, D.. *Purépecha Y Pescado: Food, Status, and Conquest in 16th Century Michoacán*. Master of Arts Thesis. OhioLINK Electronic Theses and Dissertations Center: University of Toledo, 2017.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Notes: Studies confirm the presence of an urban road network that defined boundaries of "social-spatial areas", such as lands for farming and housing architecture (Solinis-Casparius, 2019).

Reference: Solinis-Casparius, R., "Mesoamerican Urban Road Network: An Analysis of Pedestrian Pathways of Angamuco, Michoacán". *Latin American Antiquity* 33, no. 3 (2022): 464–84.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— Sí

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Notes: The system was managed by an organized bureaucracy operating under the Cazonci. Local chiefs were then responsible for collecting tribute in their respective regions. Tributary communities provided basic goods such as maize, beans, chili, firewood, and cotton, as well as luxury items like feathers, precious metals, and turquoise. (Pollard, 1993; Paredes, 1984)

Reference: Pollard, H.P. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

Reference: Paredes, C.. "El Sistema Tributario Prehispánico Entre Los Tarascos". In *El Modo De Producción Tributario En Mesoamérica*. Yucatán: Escuela de Ciencias Antropológicas, Universidad de Yucatán, 1984.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

— Yes

Notes: The Purépecha maintained a state-organized militia (Pollard, 2016), with appointed military officials, including a head of the armed forces and various commanders designated to lead distinct units during times of war.

Reference: Pollard, H.P., S. Kurnick, and J. Baron. "Ruling "purépecha Chichimeca" in a Tarascan World". In *Political Strategies in Pre-columbian Mesoamerica*. United States: University Press of Colorado, 2016.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

— Sí

Notes: The Petámuti, a high official appointed by The Cazonci, was responsible for administering justice. Justice was understood from a moral and religious point of view, meaning the role involved both judicial and ritual functions (Garcia, 2012).

Reference: Garcia, D.E.. *Materials of the Sacred: 16th to 18th Century Religious Materiality in Michoacán*. Master of Arts Thesis. Riverside: University of California , 2012.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: As described by Alcalá (2008), the Equata Consquaro ceremony could result in bodily sacrifice to Curicaueri, particularly for war prisoners, whereas moral transgressions were often addressed through varying forms of social exclusion (Pollard, 1993).

Reference: de Alcalá , Jerónimo. *Relación De Michoacán*. México: El Colegio de Michoacán, 2008.

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Traditions such as rituals and practices, were transmitted orally across generations; the Equata Consquaro ceremony provides evidence for an established normative system (Pollard, 1993), though there's no evidence any of it was in writing.

Reference: Pollard, H.P.. *Tariacuri's Legacy: The Pre Hispanic Tarascan State*. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1993.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: The military structure, led by capitanes (military leaders) and quangariecha (unit commanders) (Pollard, 2016), was organized for both conquest and defense, while also serving in ritual warfare and playing an auxiliary role in state ceremonies such as the Equata Consquaro, during which some captives were spared from sacrifice and incorporated into the army (Carvajal Medina, 2023).

Reference: Pollard, H.P., S. Kurnick, and J. Baron. "Ruling "purépecha Chichimeca" in a Tarascan World". In *Political Strategies in Pre-columbian Mesoamerica*. United States: University Press of Colorado, 2016.

Reference: Carvajal Medina, Ricardo. *The Tarascan-mexica Wars, 1476-1521*. Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, 2023.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It is unclear to what extent the Purepecha had their own written system of communication. Authors like Reyes García (1991) argue that the Purepecha possessed their own writing system, but it was lost after Spanish arrival.

Reference: Reyes García, C.. "Manuscritos Purhépechas De La Época Colonial". *Relaciones (COLMICH, Zamora)* 12, no. 48 (1991): 177-85.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The Purépecha neither documented nor orally transmitted the traditional Mexica 260-day ritual cycle. According to Kuákari (2022) they perceived and divided time across the year agricultural, lunar, and ritual cycles unique to their worldview. Very little has been formally documented about the specific dates and cycles, thus the actual calendar structure remains only theoretical.

Reference: Kuákari, H.. *Miukúa (the Purépecha Calendar)*. United States: Barnes & Noble Press, 2022.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Sí

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Recolección

– Caza (incluyendo animales marinos)

– Agricultura a pequeña escala/jardines hortícolas o huertos

– Agricultura a gran escala (ej. monocultivos, sistemas de irrigación organizados)

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